

Online Repository 4: Flowchart of patients referred for allergy evaluation

Patients referred for allergy evaluation due to suspected hypersensitivity to biologics used for in the treatment of autoimmune or inflammatory diseases.

Flowchart of patients referred for allergy evaluation. Based on the allergist's recommendations, the referring physician chose to either reintroducing a culprit biologic (in own department, via DPT or RDD), or introduce an treatment alternative. The choice of treatment for 37 patients and the outcome of the chosen treatment strategy are depicted here.

Abbreviations: **DPT**: Drug Provocation Test, **ICT**, **RDD**: Rapid Drug Desensitisation